

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New Flavones

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A number of variously substituted flavones have been synthesised and tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities. The structures of these compounds were confirmed by ir, pmr and elemental analysis.

SIGNIFICANT physiological activities¹⁻⁸ have been found in a number of 4-oxochromones. Therefore it was decided to explore methods for synthesising flavones of various kinds. The susceptibility of chromone ring system to alkali, various nucleophiles and oxidising agents restricts the range of the reaction used in the synthesis.

The synthesis involved acetylation of various substituted-phenols followed by Fries migration in the presence of anhydrous Lewis acid to the corresponding *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (2). These on esterification with substituted benzoic acids yielded corresponding substituted phenolic esters (3). These esters further undergo Baker-Venkataraman transformation^{4,5} to the respective aroylacetophenones (4). The reaction of 4 with substituted benzaldehydes in the presence of strong alkali gave substituted-acrylophenones (5). These when cyclised in the presence of H₂O₂ and alkali afforded targeted flavones (6) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

The melting points of all the compounds were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were recorded in TFA solution using TMS as internal reference. The purity of the compounds in addition to

elemental analysis was checked by tlc. Characterisation data is given in Table 1.

The following general procedure was used for the synthesis of the compounds.

3-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-1(p)-methoxybenzoylpropan-1,3-dione (4, sl. no 7): A mixture of compounds 3 (2.84 g, 0.01 mol) and potassium hydroxide (2.8 g, 0.05 mol) in dry pyridine (25 ml) was stirred mechanically for ~ 30 min, and allowed to stand for ~ 0.5 h. The reaction mixture on acidification with dilute HCl gave yellow product which was recrystallised from ethanol, (78%, 2.22 g), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 71.81; H, 5.60. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 71.83; H, 5.63%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 500 (OH), 1 640 (C=O conjugated) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (phenyl stretch); δ (TFA) 2.1 (2H, s, CH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.9-8 (7H, m, ArH).

2-Hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(p-methoxybenzoyl)-3-(p-chlorophenyl)acrylophenone (5, sl. no. 7): The compound 4 (1.42 g, 0.005 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) was added to *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.70 g, 0.005 mol) and piperidine (0.3 ml), and the mixture was stirred mechanically at 60°, then ice-cooled. The separated solid was collected at the suction pump and recrystallised from ethanol, (85%, 1.14 g), m.p. 63° (Found: C, 70.86; H, 4.65. C₂₄H₁₉O₄Cl requires: C, 70.87; H, 4.67%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 500 (OH), 1 640 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (TFA) 2.3 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.6 (1H, s, C=CH) and 7.8 (11H, m, ArH).

6-Methyl-2-(p-chlorophenyl)-3-(p-methoxybenzyl)chromone (6, sl. no. 7): The solution of the compound 5 (0.41 g, 0.001 mol) was dissolved in methanol (70 ml) and 2N NaOH (20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring and occasional cooling followed by the addition of H₂O₂ (18%; 9 ml). The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The yellow coloured solid separated was recrystallised from ethanol, (70%, 0.29 g), m.p. 212° (Found: C, 71.18; H, 4.18. C₂₄H₁₇O₄Cl requires: C, 71.18; H, 4.42%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 620 (C=O), 1 555 (C=C) and 1 350 cm⁻¹ (C-O); δ (TFA) 2.35 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.8-8.2 (11H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF FLAVONES (6)

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Y ₁	Y ₂	Y ₃	Z	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	NO ₂	65	152
2.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	Cl	H	70	103
3.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	NO ₂	65	174
4.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	OH=CH ₂	NO ₂	75	170
5.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	H	70	147
6.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	OH=CH ₂	NO ₂	65	164
7.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	OCH ₃	Cl	70	212
8.	H	CH ₃	H	H	OH	H	Cl	75	170
9.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	65	142
10.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	Cl	60	128
11.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	H	Cl	65	211
12.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	OCH ₃	Cl	70	230
13.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	Cl	75	168
14.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	NO ₂	H	70	70
15.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	NO ₂	Cl	72	231
16.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	N(CH ₃) ₂	Cl	68	175
17.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	OH=CH ₂	Cl	70	214
18.	H	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	NO ₂	73	132
19.	H	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	OH	Cl	70	140
20.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	OCH ₃	OH	Cl	65	215
21.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	Cl	68	198
22.	H	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	71	145
23.	H	CH ₃	H	OH	H	H	H	72	171
24.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	OCH ₃	OH	NO ₂	75	160
25.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	NO ₂	70	160
26.	H	CH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	NO ₂	60	210
27.	H	CH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	Cl	65	204
28.	OH ₂	H	H	H	H	OH=CH ₂	NO ₂	72	187
29.	OH ₂	H	H	H	H	OH	NO ₂	75	75
30.	H	OH ₂	NO ₂	OH	H	H	Cl	68	226

Biological activity: The compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity. *Aspergillus niger* was used for antifungal screening. The compounds were tested at 150 ppm concentration in acetone and the activity was measured in terms of growth inhibition in mm. The compounds of sl. nos. 8, 9, 12, 18, 24, 25, 26 and 30 showed moderate antifungal activity (zone of inhibition, 6–8 mm).

Antibacterial activity was evaluated by testing the compounds at 100 ppm concentration in acetone against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*. The

compounds of sl. nos. 8, 9, 11, 12, 16, 17, 25, 27 and 30 showed moderate antibacterial activity.

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